

D.0.3 Dissemination plan

WP 0 Project coordination

Responsible Partner: DTU

Contributing partners: ANSES, SSI, UCM, INRA, IP, APHA, ISS, IZSAM, IZSLER, RIVM, WBVR, PIWET, SLV, FOHM, SVA

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D.0.3 (JIP IA 2.1-WP0-T1)		
Project Acronym	EJP CARE		
Author	Rene S. Hendriksen, DTU		
Other contributors	Susanne Karlslose Pedersen, DTU		
Due month of the report	M26 (February 2020)		
Actual submission month	M30 (June 2020)		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R	Save date: 15-Jun-20	
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU	This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):	
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>	
	National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>		
	EFSA <input type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other	international	stakeholder(s):
	Social Media:		
	Other recipient(s):		

EJP CARE DISSEMINATION PLAN

For communication in relation to the EJP CARE project, several platforms and setups will be applied.

Information will be disseminated to the EJP CARE partners by allowing them to access it in one of the available platforms or by actively forwarding them the relevant information in an email.

The plan is as follows:

- 1) Sharesite:
 - a. A common **working space** for which all EJP CARE project participants are able to login and share/work in documents.
 - b. Further details in relation to access of the Sharepoint are circulated directly to the EJP CARE project participants.
- 2) EJP CARE group on the OHEJP website:
 - a. **Document repository** that allows access to e.g. list of email addresses (edits in uploaded documents is not possible).
 - b. It is a private group for EJP CARE project partners.
 - c. EJP CARE project partner is encouraged to request access to the group (see <https://onehealthjep.eu/> -> Login (or register) via the link in the top, right corner -> click on 'groups' in the top, right corner -> search for the 'CARE'-group and request access.
- 3) Deliverables will be setup following the procedure in Appendix 1 and disseminated following the procedure in Appendix 2a and Appendix 2b describing 'Dissemination of the scientific publications', 'dissemination of JIP & JRP projects deliverables', 'document repositories as well as the 'Scientific Dissemination Procedure'.
Deliverables will be accessible via the EJP CARE group on the OHEJP website.
- 4) Regular project management meetings (bi-weekly) and WP leads' meeting (bi-weekly). Minutes from bi-weekly WP leads' meeting are circulated to all partners for information. WP-leads will be the hub of information dissemination between the project management team and the WP participants and will ensure buy-in by keeping good contact (info by email as well as WP telephone conferences) with the WP participants and keeping them informed of the project status.
- 5) News updates will be sent by email directly to the EJP CARE contact persons.
- 6) Via the EJP CARE website (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-care/>) project information may be publically shared.

Appendix 1: Deliverable Template (available as a word document in the Sharesite)

Appendix 2a: Dissemination procedures and overview of documents repositories

Appendix 2b: Scientific Dissemination Procedure

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Deliverable

Workpackage

Responsible Partner:
Contributing partners:

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	
Project Acronym	
Author	
Other contributors	
Due month of the report	
Actual submission month	
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, DEC, other Save date: 15-Jun-20
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

TITLE

Title 1

1. Subtitle

1.1. Subtitle

1.1.1. Subtitle

DISSEMINATION OF JIP & JRP PROJECTS DELIVERABLES

DOCUMENTS REPOSITORIES

	REPOSITORY NAME	SYSTEM CURATOR	ACCESS RIGHTS ADMINISTRATOR	LINK
	OHEJP Website PMT Group	Comms Team	Comms Team	https://onehealthjep.eu/groups/programme-management-team/
	OHEJP Website Projects Group	Comms Team	Project Leader	https://onehealthjep.eu/groups/
	ZENODO	Comms Team	Comms Team	OHEJP repository: https://zenodo.org/communities/ohejp?page=1&size=20 To sign up on Zenodo:: https://zenodo.org/signup
	OPENAIRE	Comms Team	Comms Team	https://explore.openaire.eu/search/publication?articleId=od_____2659::a17186d0af582b509fa36f54d1b083f4

Key Contacts

OHEJP Comms Team: OHEJPcommunications@surrey.ac.uk

This email address should only be used to send finalised deliverables, scientific publications and to notify the Comms Team for any project specific meetings and events

WP3 team : ohejp@sciensano.be

WP4 team: karin.artursson@sva.se / marie.nykvist@sva.se

Scientific Dissemination Procedure

**WP1 Coordination and
Management**

**WP2 Integrative Strategic
Research Agenda**

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: BfR, INSA, IP, ISS, NVI, RIVM,
SCIENSANO, SSI, UCM, UoS, WbvR

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	Dissemination Procedure
WP and Task	WP1, WP2
Leader	ANSES
Other contributors	BfR, INSA, IP, ISS, NVI, RIVM, SCIENSANO, SSI, UCM, UoS, WbvR
Due month of the deliverable	N/A
Actual finalization month	DEC 2019
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>See the updated Grant Agreement</i>
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s):..... Social Media: Other recipient(s):

Dissemination Procedure

Interdependencies between Work Packages of the One Health EJP (OHEJP)

This document describes the [flow of outputs](#) (i.e. OHEJP, JRP, JIP and PhD deliverables and publications) [during their drafting and finalization](#) with the aim of maximizing efficiency of dissemination [within and outside the OHEJP](#). The specific actions of WP Leaders, Project Leaders, and their respective collaborators, in addition to the Communication Team (ComTeam) and Support Team (ST), are described step-wise.

OHEJP deliverables, i.e. official deliverables for which Work packages WP1 to WP7 teams of the One Health EJP are responsible

1. The ST follows up the submission dates of deliverables and sends reminders to the OHEJP WP Leaders 30 to 45 days before the submission deadline. The submission dates are a recurrent item addressed at the PMT regular conference calls or meetings.
2. The OHEJP WP Leader who is in charge of drafting a new OHEJP deliverable, uploads the nearly final version on the website space of the PMT (the “PMT Group”, which also includes the PMT collaborators). He/she makes sure that on the first pages of the document (i.e. Document Management, see annex 1) the partners are indicated that should preferentially be informed about the deliverable (the beneficiaries). The author sends an email to all PMT members (with the PMT collaborators, ST and the ComTeam in the cc) to inform the successful upload on the "PMT Group", possibly joining the document in attachment. In this way, the PMT members and PMT collaborators can monitor strategic developments (WP2) and identify information relevant for stakeholders (WP5) or for sustainability plans (WP7). PMT members may comment on the suggested beneficiaries and inform the ComTeam.
3. The PMT validates the document, preferably within 1 to 2 weeks. The OHEJP WP Leader then sends the final version of the deliverable to the ST, which puts it on the participant portal of the European Commission (EC). The ST then informs the ComTeam that this action is completed.
4. The ComTeam uploads the deliverable on the private space “EJP Consortium Members Group” and sends the document to the beneficiaries as identified.
5. If it is a [public](#) deliverable and upon agreement of the PMT, ComTeam puts the deliverable on Zenodo (Open Access) with a link on the open space of the OHEJP website (preferably in a clearly visible dedicated space).

Project deliverables, i.e. JRP and JIP outcomes that are produced during the life span of the projects

1. The Project Leader puts the nearly final version of the deliverable on the private space of the project (“Project Group”)
2. The Project Leader consults with the project consortium for validation of the deliverable, and for any argument as to whether the deliverable should be confidential (all deliverables are public by default). This justification should be mentioned on the first pages of the document (i.e. Document Management, see annex 2). Also, the author indicates in the

Document Management section (see annex 2) the partners that should preferentially be informed about the deliverable (the beneficiaries).

3. After validation, the Project Leader sends the project deliverable with clear explanation of the objectives and the content, and with the information as requested in the document Management section (i.e. public or confidential, with justification; beneficiaries) to the WP3 Leader (research project) or WP4 Leader (integrative project) and to the ComTeam. The latter uploads it to the “PMT Group”. They inform by email PMT members so that the PMT members and PMT collaborators can monitor strategic developments (WP2) and identify information relevant for stakeholders (WP5) or for sustainability plans (WP7). Under the “Description” part the objectives, the content and the above-mentioned reasoning concerning the preferred confidential nature of the document are copied.
4. The PMT may discuss with the Project Leader on the confidential status of the document and should arrive at an agreement in a reasonable period of time.
5. The WP3/WP4 leaders keep track of the project deliverables as a means to monitor the progress of the project. WP3/WP4 send the document to the beneficiaries as identified.
6. If the project deliverable is a [public](#) document, the Project Leader uploads it in Zenodo. On the Zenodo platform, the Project Leader fills in the information and metadata required on the upload form and pays particular attention to include the reference to the OHEJP grant agreement.

Note: If a publication and/or a data is related to the deliverable, the author will link them in the Zenodo form. Then, the author submits the deliverable and sends an email to inform the ComTeam. The ComTeam can curate and finalize the submission.

Scientific publications

1. The lead author of the manuscript (a project collaborator, the PhD student or a PMT member/collaborator) consults the OHEJP Scientific Publication Policy and carefully follows these instructions.
2. The lead author shares the nearly final version of the manuscript with the respective project consortium or members of the PhD accompanying panel. In case of a PMT member or PMT collaborator, he/she shares the manuscript with the PMT, including the PMT collaborators. The private groups on the OHEJP website can be used to that end.
3. The pre-submission process, i.e. the consultation and approval phase with the co-authors, is described in the Publication Policy and should be carefully followed. The lead author submits the manuscript.
4. The lead author sends the submitted manuscript to the ComTeam, which uploads it on the “PMT Group” and informs the PMT and its collaborators. In this way, the PMT members and collaborators can monitor strategic developments (WP2) and identify information relevant for stakeholders (WP5) or for sustainability plans (WP7).
5. When accepted for publication or if available in a preprint server, the manuscript is made openly accessible (open access policy) by the lead author in Zenodo. The author also fills in the information and metadata required on the Zenodo upload form and sends the link or the publication to the ComTeam that can curate and finalize the submission in Zenodo. If a paper needs major modifications or is to be submitted to a different journal, the lead author should go through all the steps again (see also the Scientific Publication Policy).
6. The ComTeam puts a link on the open space of the website and uploads the publication to OpenAIRE.

Annex 1. Document Management section of the OHEJP deliverables

Title OHEJP deliverable	
WP and task	
Leader	
Other contributors	
Due month of the deliverable	
Actual submission month	
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, DEC, other Save date: 18-Dec-19
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>See updated Grant Agreement</i>
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p><u>Other recipient(s):</u></p>

Annex 2. Document Management section of the Project deliverables

JIP/JRP deliverable	
Project Acronym	
Author	
Other contributors	
Due month of the report	
Actual submission month	
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.;</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R, DEC, other Save date: 18-Dec-19
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